

MOISTURE STABILITY AND MECHANICAL DURABILITY OF PEAT BIOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Peat, the organic matter formed from incomplete degradation of vegetation in peatlands, was studied as lignocellulosic raw material in manufacture of biocomposites. Peat mosses with varying degree of decomposition, namely slightly decomposed peat (H2) and moderately decomposed peat (H6), were ground into different particle size fractions which were used to prepare peat-polypropylene (PP) composites with 50 wt% peat content using extrusion compounding. The moisture absorption and dimensional stability as well as the mechanical properties and microstructure before and after cyclic freeze-thaw conditioning of the peat-PP composites were analysed and compared to reference wood-plastic composite (WPC). The mechanical properties of peat-PP composites were better than the properties of reference WPC before the freeze-thaw conditioning, and the mechanical permanence of peat-PP composites was better after the cyclic conditioning. Especially when peat with higher decomposition degree was used (H6), the mechanical permanence of peat-PP composites was improved. Likewise, the moisture absorption and the dimensional stability properties were improved the more decomposed the used peat was. The particle size did not affect the composite properties as much as the decomposition degree of peat, though the dimensional stability of peat-PP composite with moderately decomposed peat was better with smaller particle size peat.

1 INTRODUCTION

Natural lignocellulosic fibres have become as viable alternatives for synthetic or inorganic materials in polymer matrix composites. Lignocellulosic materials have the advantage of biodegradability, renewability, wide availability, low density, competitive specific mechanical properties and relatively low cost. The lignocellulose-filled polymer composites, such as wood-plastic composites (WPCs), are advertised as low-maintenance and high-durability products although their permanence in outdoor environments is still a concern [1–3]. The drawbacks of such biocomposites are related to their high moisture absorption, dimensional instability and poor adhesion between hydrophilic lignocellulose material and the hydrophobic polymers [2,4].

Due to these drawbacks of hydrophilic lignocelluloses, peat, the organic substance formed by incomplete degradation of plant biomass in fens, bogs, salt marshes and some swamps in various parts of the world [5,6], is an interesting lignocellulosic material as it has hydrophobic characteristics. Before drying peat has hydrophilic nature, but after dehydration it changes from hydrophilic to hydrophobic [7]. The hydrophobicity of peat increases also with the increasing degree of decomposition, as the content of hydrophilic cellulose and hemicellulose decrease and the content of hydrophobic substances such as waxes and lignin increase [8].

The quality and composition of peat varies depending on the depth, age, plant matter and drainage regime of the peatland [6]. To assess the degree of decomposition of the original lignocellulosic plants, peats are classified according to their degree of humification [5,8]. In the von Post scale, 10 classes of

humification are used from H1 (undecomposed, plant structures are unaltered) to H10 (no recognisable plant structures) [8,9]. The composition of peat is affected by the degradation of the different chemical groups in the plant matter: plant waxes are quite resistant to degradation while starches and water-soluble sugars are easily degradable. Cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin are found in varying extents in peats as they may have high resistance to degradation [5]. In general, the amount of cellulose and hemicellulose are lower with increasing degrees of humification as the amount of lignin is higher [8].

Due to its special properties, peat is an interesting material for biocomposites. The hydrophobic nature of peat could improve the adhesion with hydrophobic thermoplastics and lead to less moisture sensitive materials. In the study by Immonen 2010 peat fibre-composites with 20 % and 40 % peat fibre were produced and the results were promising as peat fibre composites had lower water absorption compared to other lignocellulose composites [10]. In this study the aim was to investigate the potential of peat material for composite production by studying how peat decomposition rate and particle size affect their mechanical properties and moisture resistance under cyclic conditions.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Two peat samples (Vapo Oy, Finland) of different decomposition degrees were used as lignocellulose materials. Based on von Post's classification, the first peat sample was of decomposition degree H2 (slightly decomposed) and the other of H6 (moderately decomposed). The peat samples were first pre-grinded using a knife mill equipped with a screen with 4 mm openings after which they were grinded into two particle size fractions using 50 ZPS Circoplex air classifier mill (Hosokawa Alpine, Germany) and grinding speed of 20 000 rpm. To obtain different particle size fractions, fine and coarse, air classifier speeds of 2000 rpm and 10000 rpm were used. The peat samples were ground in 30 wt% moisture content and dried in an oven at 105 °C to reach moisture content below 1%. Polypropylene (PP) homopolymer 194-NA25 (INEOS Olefins and Polymers Europe) with a melt flow index of 25g/10 min (230 °C/2.16 kg) was used as the matrix polymer. Commercial WPC decking board was used as the reference material. The reference WPC contained 30 wt% cellulose fibres and had a PP matrix.

2.2 Composite processing

Peat composites with 50 wt% peat content were melt compounded with PP using a co-rotating twin-screw extruder (ZSK-18 MEGALab, Coperion W&P, Germany). The temperature profile in extrusion was from 160 °C to 180 °C, and the rotational speed used in the compounding was 250 rpm. The peat composites were profiled into a rectangular profile with a cross section of 3 mm x 18 mm. The profiles were further compression moulded into specimens having dimensions of 150 mm x 50 mm x 4 mm with a hydraulic press (LabEcon 300, Fontijne Presses, the Netherlands) and metal frame using 180 °C temperature and 6.7 MPa pressure.

2.3 Characterisation

Laser diffraction analyser (Beckman Coulter LS 13320, USA) was used to analyse the particle size distributions of the ground peat sample fractions. Standard methods for sodium hydroxide solubility (TAPPI T212), Klason lignin (TAPPI T222), acetone soluble extractives (TAPPI T280) and ash content (TAPPI T211) were used to analyse the chemical composition of peat samples. The cellulose content was determined according to Kürchner-Hoffner method [11]. Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM Zeiss Sigma, Carl Zeiss, Germany) was used to study the morphology of peat particles as well as the fracture surface microstructure of the composites. Fracture surfaces were made by breaking the specimens after freezing them in liquid nitrogen. The FESEM specimens were sputter coated with a 6-nm layer of platinum before observation.

The composite specimens were subjected to moisture and cyclic freeze-thaw conditions according to standard test methods. The swelling and water absorption was analysed according to EN 317 and

EN 15534-1 and the moisture resistance under cyclic conditions according to EN 321 and EN 15534-1. The cyclic conditioning consisted of three cycles, each comprising immersion in water, freezing, and drying (70°C). The mechanical properties were measured before and after the cyclic treatment according to EN 310 test method (three-point bending) using Z010 TH Allround universal testing machine (Zwick GmbH & Co.KG, Germany) and 10 kN load cell and 5 mm/min testing speed. Nine (9) replicates for each formulation was tested. For the peat composites the sample size was 4 mm x 50 mm x 150 mm whereas for the commercial WPC the sample size was 7 mm x 50 mm x 190 mm. To evaluate the permanence of the mechanical properties of the composites, retention ratios (RR) for modulus of elasticity (MOE RR) and flexural strength (MOR RR) were calculated according to Chen et al. 2016 [12]:

$$MOE_{RR} = MOE_{after} / MOE_{before} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$MOR_{RR} = MOR_{after} / MOR_{before} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where MOE_{before}, MOR_{before}, MOE_{after} and MOR_{after} are the modulus of elasticity and flexural strength before and after cyclic testing.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Peat characterisation

The chemical composition of the peat samples is shown in Table 1. In the less decomposed H2 peat the amount of lignin, extractives and ash are lower than in the more decomposed H6 peat. The average and median particle sizes of the peat samples after grinding into fine and coarse particle size fractions are also shown in Table 1. The H2_fine and H6_fine particle fractions had median particles sizes of 12 µm and 17 µm, respectively, and the coarse fractions, H2_coarse and H6_coarse, had median particle sizes of 219 µm and 361 µm, respectively.

	Chemical composition			Particle size		
	H2	H6	Method	Fraction	Average (µm)	Median (µm)
NaOH solubility ¹	57.2	78.2	TAPPI T212	H2_fine	24	17
Lignin	21.8	47.4	TAPPI T222	H2_coarse	391	361
Extractives	4.6	7.3	TAPPI T280	H6_fine	16	12
Cellulose	19.6	12.0	Kürchner-Hoffner	H6_coarse	269	219
Ash	1.3	3.1	TAPPI T211			

¹Sodium hydroxide soluble substances such as hemicellulose and degraded cellulose.

Table 1: The chemical composition of peats H2 and H6 as well as the average and median particle sizes of the ground peat samples.

The FESEM images in Figure 1 show the morphology of peat fractions after grinding. Pieces of plant cell walls can be distinguished in the fractions with larger particle size (H2_coarse, H6_coarse) which are no longer visible when the particle size is decreasing (H2_fine, H6_fine) and thus the material appears to be more homogenous when particle size is smaller. Overall, there are no great differences in the morphology of peat particles between the H2 and H6 samples.

Figure 1: FESEM images of the coarse and fine peat particle fractions of H2 and H6 decomposition degrees used in peat-PP composites.

3.2 Swelling and water absorption of peat composites

The swelling and water absorption of the peat composites made with the different particle size fractions of H2 and H6 peats and reference WPC are presented in Figure 2. After 28 days of immersion in water, the thickness swelling of the composites made with more decomposed H6 peat was the lowest whereas the composites with less decomposed H2 peat and commercial WPC were quite similar. In the case of H6 peat composites, decrease in peat particle size appears to reduce the thickness swelling of the composites, which might be due to more homogenous composite.

Figure 2: Thickness swelling (left) and water absorption (right) of peat composites with different decomposition degrees (H2, H6) and particle sizes (fine, coarse) and reference WPC after 28 days of immersion in water.

The water absorption after 28 days (Fig. 2) was lowest for the H6 peat composite made with smallest peat particle size fraction (H6_fine, median particle size 12 µm). Overall, the peat composites with H6 peat had similar water absorption properties as the commercial WPC, between 4 % and 8 %. The lower water absorption of H6 peat composites in comparison to H2 peat composites is related to the higher amount of lignin and lower content of cellulose. Likewise, higher content of hydrophobic components, lignin and extractives, were found to decrease the water uptake of WPC in a study by Bouafif et al. 2009 [13].

For the H2 peat composites the water absorption was over 10 %, and opposed to the H6 peat composites, the composite with larger particle size peat (H2_coarse) had the lowest water absorption. The H2 peat had higher cellulose content than H6 peat (Table 1), thus it was expected that water absorption and thickness swelling of H2 peat composites was higher compared to H6 peat composites. The increased amount of hydrophilic surfaces due to smaller particle size could be the reason for higher water absorption of composites with smaller H2 peat particles (H2_fine) in comparison to H2_composite made with larger particle size H2 peat (H2_coarse).

3.3 Mechanical properties and durability of peat composites

The flexural strength and modulus of peat composites were measured before and after cyclic freeze-thaw conditioning and the results are presented in Figure 3. The retention ratios for flexural strength (MOR RR) and modulus (MOE RR) after conditioning are presented in Figure 4. The flexural strengths of all the peat composites before cyclic conditioning were better than the commercial WPC's, and the decomposition degree or particle size of peat did not have great effect on the strength values. After freeze-thaw conditioning the strength properties of the peat composites were maintained clearly better than the strength of commercial WPC's, as Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 show. The stiffness of peat composites decreased 46-73 % after the cyclic conditioning as can be seen from Fig. 3. The peat composites maintained their stiffness significantly better than the commercial WPC, which maintained only 15% of its original stiffness. The composite with fine H6 peat particles (H6_fine) had the highest MOE after conditioning (73 %).

Figure 3: Effect of cyclic freeze-thaw conditioning on the flexural strength (left) and modulus of elasticity (right) of peat composites with different decomposition degrees (H2, H6) and particle sizes (fine, coarse) and reference WPC.

Figure 4: Retention ratio of flexural strength (MOR RR) and flexural modulus (MOE RR) of peat composites and reference WPC after cyclic freeze-thaw conditioning.

3.4 Microstructure after freeze-thaw conditioning

The fracture surfaces of peat composites with H2_coarse and H6_fine peat fractions as well as reference WPC's after freeze-thaw conditioning are shown in Fig. 5. The peat composite with H2_coarse peat had the lowest flexural strength and MOE of the peat composites after cyclic conditioning, and from Fig. 5 (image on left) it can be seen that the composite fracture surface is very uneven and there are gaps from particle pull-outs indicating poor adhesion between PP matrix and H2 peat particles. The H6_fine sample (Fig. 5, middle image) on the other hand had the highest mechanical permanence and best moisture stability of the peat composites. The microstructure of H6_fine composite is more homogenous due to lack of larger peat particles when compared to H2_coarse composite, and it is not as easy to distinguish individual peat particles from the matrix. Some gaps are also visible in H6_fine sample indicating lack of adhesion, however, the size of these gaps is smaller when compared to H2_coarse. The fracture surface of reference WPC (Fig. 5, image on right) is quite uneven and also fibre pull-outs can be observed due to poor adhesion with matrix and cellulose fibres which might be the reason for lower strength properties of WPC in comparison with peat composites.

Figure 5: Fracture surfaces the H2_coarse and H6_fine peat composite samples and reference WPC after freeze-thaw conditioning.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Peat-PP composites with 50 wt% peat content were successfully melt compounded using H2 and H6 peat in different particle size fractions (fine and coarse). The thickness swelling and moisture absorption properties of peat-PP composites were similar to commercial reference WPC, and even better when peat with higher decomposition degree (H6) and smaller particle size was used due to lower amount of hydrophilic components in more decomposed peat. The mechanical properties of peat-PP composites were better than reference WPC's and their mechanical permanence was much better after cyclic freeze-thaw conditioning. The degree of peat decomposition had the greatest effect on the retention of mechanical properties, and effect of peat particle size was smaller. Because of good moisture stability and durability, peat-PP composites have potential to be used in outdoor applications and humid conditions.

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